

		DEMOGRAPHY			GENETIC	
		POPULATION OCCUPANCY	ABUNDANCE OF INDIVIDUALS	POPULATION PERFORMANCE (Vital rates)	DIVERSITY	DIFFERENTIATION
DIMENSIONS	GEOGRAPHY C: range centre P: range periphery	a				
	HISTORY O: old populations Y: young populations	f <u>Secondary effect</u>	g <u>Secondary effect</u>	h <u>Secondary effect</u>	i	
	ECOLOGY C: niche centre M: niche margin	k Rate & species-dependent	n <u>Secondary effect</u>	o <u>Secondary effect</u>		
DISTRIBUTION	HYPOTHESIS REFRAMED	p				
<p>Conditions (if not respected, curves might be reshaped and factors considered as secondary might reach significance):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The range must be continuous The species must have only one main refugial area The range must be stable on short term The species range must have been impacted significantly by past environmental changes (e.g. glaciations) 						